

THE FOURTH WORLD CONGRESS ON ANALOGY

Crete, Greece, August 29-31, 2025

HANDBOOK

Edited by

Katarzyna Gan-Krzywoszyńska
Przemysław Krzywoszyński
Aleksandra Walas

HANDBOOK OF THE
FOURTH WORLD CONGRESS ON ANALOGY

Crete, Greece
August 29-31, 2025
www.analogycongress.com

Handbook of the Fourth World Congress on Analogy

Crete, Greece, August 29-31, 2025

EDITED BY

Katarzyna Gan-Krzywoszyńska, Przemysław Krzywoszyński, Aleksandra Walas

COPYRIGHT BY

© Katarzyna Gan-Krzywoszyńska, Przemysław Krzywoszyński, Aleksandra Walas
Publishing House KONTEKST, Poland, 2025

REVIEWER

Andrzej Indrzejczak, University of Łódź, Poland

PROOFREADING

Benilda Siłkowska-Mąsior

COVER PHOTOS BY

Katarzyna Gan-Krzywoszyńska, Przemysław Krzywoszyński, Aleksandra Walas

www.analogycongress.com

ISBN 978-83-68332-10-0

PRINTED IN POLAND

Printing Plant Moś & Łuczak

 Kontekst
Publishing House

SCIENTIFIC PUBLISHER

POZNAŃ – POLAND
kontekst2@o2.pl
www.wkn.com.pl

Contents

1. About the Congress: 10 Years of the Project	7
2. Juan Manuel Campos Benítez <i>In Memoriam</i>	9
Katarzyna GAN-KRZYWOSZYŃSKA, Przemysław KRZYWO- SZYŃSKI, Piotr LEŚNIEWSKI – <i>Juan Manuel Campos</i> <i>Benítez: In Memoriam</i>	10
Gabriela JIMÉNEZ BANDALA – <i>Reflections on the Legacy</i> <i>of Juan Manuel Campos Benítez: Logic, Pedagogy, and</i> <i>Humanity</i>	13
3. Organizing Committee	21
4. Abstracts of Keynote Talks	23
Jean-Yves BEZIAU – <i>What is Analogy?</i>	23
Tatiana DENISOVA – <i>Hermeneutic Pitfalls of Analogy</i>	25
Marcin GMYS – <i>From Structural Analogy to Metaphor.</i> <i>A Musical Perspective</i>	26

Dénes NAGY – <i>The role of λόγος, ἀναλογία, and συμμετρία at the Birth of Abstract Mathematics and Aesthetics: In Memoriam Władysław Tatarkiewicz (1886-1980), Stanisław Jaśkowski (1906-1965), and Árpád Szabó (1913-2001)</i>	28
Marcin J. SCHROEDER – <i>Reincarnations and Consequences of the Distinction Between Analog and Digital Information</i>	31
Ioannis VANDOULAKIS – <i>Ratio, Proportionality and Similarity in Greek Mathematics and Philosophy</i>	35
5. Abstracts of Contributed Talks	37
Luca BIANCHINI, Anna TROMBETTA – <i>Hidden Messages and Cultural Resistance: Political Analogies in Italian Music and Literature under Foreign Rule</i>	37
Dorota BRZOZOWSKA – <i>Analog(ical) vs Digital in Sports ...</i>	41
Cyprien CARRAUD – <i>Aristotle's Analogy: Acknowledging the Mathematical Legacy, and Overcoming it</i>	43
Maira DE CINQUE – <i>Between Resemblance and Free Association: Is Any Analogy False?</i>	46
Katarzyna GAN-KRZYWOSZYŃSKA – <i>Baroque and Analogy</i>	47
José David GARCÍA-CRUZ – <i>Two Analogies of Time in the Film “The Endless” by Justin Benson and Aaron Moorhead</i>	49
Zofia HAŁĘZA – <i>History of Analogy in Polish Philosophy ...</i>	51
CP HERTOUGH – <i>Analogy as the Core of Consciousness (What It Is Like e.g. Nagel 1974)</i>	52
Betül Fatma KARAL – <i>Distinction and Difference in Dialogue</i>	53

Przemysław KRZYWOSZYŃSKI – <i>Republic as an Analogical Concept</i>	55
Juan MARQUEZ – <i>Hanging on by a Thread over Thin Ice: Hermeneutical Analogies in Cross-Cultural Philosophy</i>	57
Alex MCQUIBBAN – <i>Only the Same is Truly Similar: On Identity, the Importance of Analogy and Fragility of Conceptual Webs</i>	59
Jorge MEDINA – <i>Peculiarities of the Nomination of God as a Non-univocal Agent according to Aquinas</i>	62
Ricardo Arturo NICOLÁS FRANCISCO – <i>Similarities and Differences between “logica docens” and “logica utens” according to Juan Manuel Campos Benítez</i>	66
Fernando SANTORO, Caroline PIRES TING – <i>Diagrammatic Thought and the Aesthetics of Renewal: Translating Wényánwén across Worlds</i>	68
Vida Mia S. VALVERDE – <i>Vinyl Realism: Analogy, Authenticity, and Metaphysical Commitment in the Evolution of DJ Technology</i>	70
Miroslava TRAJKOVSKI – <i>The Semiotic Nature of Analogy</i> ..	72
Maurício VIEIRA KRITZ – <i>Wired-non-Wired Analogies</i>	74
Aleksandra WALAS – <i>Biophilia as an Analogical Concept: Philosophy, Biology and Art</i>	77
6. Notes	79

5. Abstracts of Contributed Talks ---

Hidden Messages and Cultural Resistance: Political Analogies in Italian Music and Literature under Foreign Rule

Luca BIANCHINI

Doctor of Musicology, University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy
luca.bianchini@italianopera.org

Anna TROMBETTA

Doctor of Musicology, University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy
anna.trombetta@italianopera.org

Throughout the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, Italian music and literature served as vehicles for subversive messages and coded forms of resistance against foreign domination and political censorship. This paper explores the sophisticated system of analogies, symbolic codes, and intertextual references deployed by composers and writers to circumvent repression

and communicate ideals of liberty, national identity, and cultural emancipation.

Our interdisciplinary approach combines musicology, philology, and cultural history to analyze how operatic works – often dismissed as purely entertaining or even complicit with authority – were in fact saturated with hidden meanings, frequently structured through analogy. The use of musical quotations, mythological allusions, dramaturgical parallels, and especially analogic strategies enabled artists such as Johann Simon Mayr, Gioachino Rossini, Gaetano Donizetti, and Vincenzo Bellini to create a double-layered narrative: one apparent and sanctioned, the other accessible only through analogical interpretation by informed or initiated audiences.

Among the works examined in detail in this study are Johann Simon Mayr's *Lamentazioni Sacre*, *Sisara*, *Atalia*, *San Luigi Gonzaga* (the satirical oratorio), *Verter*, *Le Danaïdi*, *Medea in Corinto*, *ATAR*, *ossia il Serraglio d'Ormus*, *Le due Duchesse*, and *La rosa bianca e la rosa rossa*, all composed between the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries. These works are particularly rich in Masonic and esoteric analogies, often using mythological and biblical figures as veiled references to contemporary political conditions and revolutionary ideals. In *San Luigi Gonzaga* and *La rosa bianca e la rosa rossa*, for example, Mayr encodes messages of fraternity and resistance, drawing on the language of secret societies and embedding allusions to the Carboneria and the wider network of political brotherhoods, as explored extensively in the present paper.

Turning to Gioachino Rossini, the analysis covers a wide chronological spectrum, from his early works such as *L'equivoco stravagante* – a sharp parody with anti-clerical and anti-monarchical undertones – through *La cambiale di matrimonio*, *L'inganno felice*, *Ciro in Babilonia*, *Demetrio e Polibio*, and *La pietra del paragone*, to masterpieces like *La gazza ladra*, which stands as a brilliant example of social analogy and political allegory. Later operas such as *Maometto secondo*, where musical borrowings function as coded signals, and *Semiramide* further demonstrate

Rossini's reliance on analogical strategies to subvert censorship. Above all, *Guillaume Tell* emerges as a direct call to political emancipation and an analogic celebration of national liberation – its revolutionary message hidden beneath layers of myth and symbol, as the detailed analysis of its libretto and score reveals.

The study also explores the profound relationship and stylistic continuity between Gaetano Donizetti and Mayr, focusing on the analogical transmission of coded language and the central role of allegory and analogy within Donizetti's operas. Works such as *Pigmalione* and *Marin Faliero* exemplify the way in which political themes and analogical devices are woven into the fabric of Donizetti's music and dramaturgy, as well as in the subtexts of his librettos – echoing the strategies of his teacher Mayr and reinforcing the clandestine dialogue among artists engaged in cultural resistance.

Finally, particular attention is given to Vincenzo Bellini's *I puritani*, viewed as the “swan song” of patriotic opera – simultaneously expressing melancholy and hope for national resurgence – and to Bellini's connections with political librettists like Carlo Pepoli. These collaborations are interpreted through the lens of analogy, as both music and text are crafted to sustain a hidden discourse on freedom and national identity, accessible only to those attuned to their deeper, symbolic meanings.

A crucial and often overlooked aspect is the political risk that artists like Rossini faced. Contrary to the cliché of the lazy or exhausted composer, Rossini's withdrawal from composition after *Guillaume Tell* was not due to lack of creativity, but to the mounting dangers of political censorship and surveillance.

His so-called “laziness” was, in fact, a prudent silence in response to a system that punished any subversive message – no matter how cleverly disguised in analogical or symbolic form. This argument is demonstrated by a detailed analysis of the librettos and the music of Rossini's operas themselves, where the use of analogy, coded references, and symbolic allusions reveals the real risks faced by the composer. The strategies of quotation, self-

borrowing, and coded messaging were not mere stylistic choices but essential survival tactics, relying heavily on analogy, in an era of dictatorships and omnipresent censors. Special attention is also devoted to the pervasive influence of the Carboneria and other secret societies, whose coded rituals, allegorical language, and clandestine networks shaped both the content and the analogical form of these works. In this context, the frequent references to “initiates,” “brotherhood,” and “sacred daggers” in librettos, the recurring presence of Masonic symbols, and the transformation of romantic plots into encrypted analogies of revolutionary struggle, are all decoded as part of a wider system of political communication. Opera theaters themselves became spaces of resistance, where musical and literary analogies could be shared safely among the “buoni cugini” (“good cousins”) and “fratelli illuminati” (“Illuminati brothers”), while escaping the literal-mindedness of official censorship.

The analysis is extended to the literary context, with attention to the analogical double meanings in librettos, the use of allegorical figures inspired by Dante, Ariosto, and Metastasio, and the role of the theater as a forum for civil education and veiled dissent – again, all made possible by the powerful device of analogy.

This paper also investigates the broader semiotic strategies of quotation and stylistic mimicry: how Mayr, for example, incorporated themes from Mozart, Haydn, or Beethoven not as plagiarism, but as analogical commentary – transforming familiar motifs into revolutionary signals. Likewise, Rossini’s adoption of archaic or popular idioms, or even satirical references in sacred works, subverts the expectations of both public and censors, often through analogy.

Ultimately, we argue that analogy functioned as a survival tool – a way to sustain and transmit collective values and political ideals in hostile environments. In periods where free speech was suppressed, the arts became a clandestine means of communication and hope. These analogies, far from being mere rhetorical devices, were the hidden lifeblood of a cultural resistance that contributed to the shaping of modern European identity.

